

ARCTIC PASSION

Deliverable 4.4

Regional Sea Ice Information Tool

Version 1

07-November-2023

101003472 | Arctic Passion

**ARCTIC
PASSION**

Work package 4

Innovating user-driven Arctic Eurogeo pilot services

Lead beneficiary

7 - MET

Lead author

Øystein Godøy (MET)

Contributors

Thomas Lavergne (MET)

Michael Yartys (MET)

Status

Submitted

Dissemination level

PU

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101003472

Table of Contents

Executive summary.....4

Introduction.....4

Requirement.....4

Implementation.....4

Future perspectives.....5

Executive summary

An interactive visualisation tool for climate indicators for sea ice extent and area, both pan-arctic and on a regional basis is developed. This tool will be integrated in the State of the Arctic Environment pilot service once that reach an appropriate maturity level. For the time being it is available in the Cryo portal operated by MET. There are 2 options for the time being, one for daily indexes at <https://cryo.met.no/en/sea-ice-index-daily> and one for monthly indexes at <https://cryo.met.no/en/sea-ice-index-monthly>. The data used are the Climate Data Records produced by the EUMETSAT Ocean and Sea Ice Satellite Application facility.

Introduction

The Arctic PASSION project is described in more detail in the project website which is available at <https://arcticpassion.eu/>. The purpose of Arctic PASSION is creation and implementation of a coherent, integrated Arctic observing system. This implies integrating already existing observing systems in a system of systems approach as well addressing gaps in the current observing system. Arctic PASSION will generate data through the project implementation, but equally important is to map and establish access to already existing datasets in support of the pilot services and other activities of Arctic PASSION.

Within Work Package 4 - INNOVATING USER-DRIVEN ARCTIC EUROGEO PILOT SERVICES, task 4.3 implements the Pilot Service State of the Arctic Environment. The ambition of this is to provide the latest scientific information in a simple manner. As part of this task a dedicated effort is focusing on development of a tool that provides interactive visualisation of sea ice information. This document provides information on the tool.

Requirement

In the project proposal the following description was provided:

An interactive visualization webpage for sea-ice (extent and area) time series is developed and accessible online. It is based on Ocean and Sea Ice Satellite Application Facility (OSI SAF) sea-ice data, and offers both hemispheric and regional indexes

This has been interpreted as development of a web service that can be embedded in any web page of interest.

Implementation

In the current development a somewhat generic tool allowing for interpretation of both daily and monthly indexes has been developed. This tool could also be used for other climate indexes, e.g. snow.

The tool is developed using Bokeh (<http://bokeh.org/>), an open source framework for interactive visualizations. The source code is freely available at <https://github.com/metno/sea-ice-index-viz> under a GNU General Public License v3. Containers for easy deployment in any infrastructure is provided through the Docker compose setup in the GitHub repository.

In order to test the tool while waiting for the Pilot Service 3: State of the Arctic Environment' service, it has been deployed in an institutional service developed at the Norwegian Meteorological Institute (MET). This service is a cryosphere information website called Cryo and is available at <https://cryo.met.no/>. Within this site a dedicated area is focusing on sea ice information and a sub area is dedicated to sea ice indexes - <https://cryo.met.no/en/sea-ice-index>. In this menu both static representations of sea ice indexes as well as dynamic/interactive visualisations are provided.

Two menu items have been provided:

1. One for daily indexes
 1. <https://cryo.met.no/en/sea-ice-index-daily>
2. One for monthly indexes
 1. <https://cryo.met.no/en/sea-ice-index-monthly>

The same tool is used for both menu items, the difference is only in the data being fed to the tool.

A screen shot of the tool as it appears in the Cryo site is provided in Figure 1.

The tool allows direct readout of values using mouse-over functionality in the web browser, there are several regional sea ice indexes for sea ice extent and area provided along with global as well as northern and southern hemisphere products.

For change detection, various reference periods are provided as methods to dig into user specified periods by selecting individual years in the tool.

At any time the user can zoom in/out, and save a graphical representation of the graph.

The tool described in this report, which provides interactive visualization of sea ice information, will be accessible through the main site of Pilot Service 3: State of the Arctic Environment' web service. Once that web site is operational and open to the public towards the end of the project, the sea ice tool will be accessible via the Sea ice indicator page of the service. We will there also add a brief explanation and text that informs about this tool as an example of how the overall service can be expanded with greater detail and flexibility also for other indicators, in later development (beyond the time frame of Arctic PASSION).

Future perspectives

The regional sea ice information tool is yet to be integrated in the State of the Arctic Environment pilot service, but this is due to the development process for the pilot service and not the tool itself. In parallel

to this integration, the tool will be further developed to add the possibility to display sea-ice forecast information. The tool is set up as a web service in the MET environment and can easily be integrated in the pilot service or other web sites like illustrated by the integration with the Cryo portal.

The tool has been demonstrated for Arctic stakeholders like the Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP), receiving positive feedback. This preliminary interaction was focused on which needs AMAP has for sea ice climate information. As the tool will be integrated in the State of the Arctic Pilot Service, the real stakeholder engagement will be done through that pilot service. The dialogue with AMAP indicated that they would like to see a combination of sea ice indicators based on observed data (like what is presented today) and sea ice indicators based on climate scenarios (i.e. climate model output) in the future. This is out of scope for Arctic PASSION, but based on the results projects like the Fram Center project [SUDARCO](#) such use of the tool can be evaluated in future projects (being considered for a ESA Destination Earth Service Service Platform use case for the Arctic). MET will continue to support and use the tool in services/web sites and also ensure that the underlying data is available in the SAON Data Portal (<https://data.arcticobserving.org/>).

Daily Sea Ice Index

Figure 1: Screenshot of the regional sea ice information tool developed at MET.